

THE IMPORTANCE OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION AND CAREER DEVELOPMENT IN SHAPING MODERN INTERNAL AFFAIRS OFFICERS

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Abstract: This article highlights the significance of continuous education and career development in training and shaping modern internal affairs officers. It analyzes the role of ongoing integration of education and professional development in ensuring that officers acquire skills and qualifications that meet contemporary requirements. Additionally, the article examines the importance of enhancing professional competencies of internal affairs officers through continuous education, improving their job performance, and ensuring public safety. Special attention is given to the implementation of modern technologies and teaching methods, as well as the impact of continuous career development.

Keywords: personnel, personnel policy, human resource management, education-career, career, careerism, organizational-tactical management, organizational-strategic management

The most crucial guarantee for establishing the legal and socio-political foundations of the rule of law is the staffing of law enforcement agencies, primarily the internal affairs bodies.

With the emergence of the state, one of its most important goals is to ensure public order. To directly implement the function of maintaining internal order in social life, the state forms a special apparatus. Today, in many countries, it is called the internal affairs system.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the internal affairs bodies carry out state service in the field of law enforcement activity (function) of the state, are considered a special service of the state, and are regulated by separate legislative acts.

Currently, the next stage of organizing personnel work is being implemented in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the current era places new demands on employees of internal affairs bodies. In order to implement priority tasks for the socio-economic development of the country at the present stage, special attention is being paid to revising management methods and increasing the effectiveness of activities.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan **Shavkat Mirziyoyev** to the Oliy Majlis, the statement "**Today, life itself demands that we form a professional, prompt, and effective civil service system, and develop an effective system for paving the way for innovative, proactive, and loyal personnel**"[1] necessitates scientific and practical research into priority areas of personnel work in the civil service, including in the internal affairs bodies.

In modern Uzbekistan, the task of combating crime has transcended the scope of a narrow departmental issue and has been elevated to the national level. Until recently, the problem of selecting, training, and placing personnel for law enforcement agencies was

typically resolved through directive methods. An analysis of the personnel situation in the internal affairs bodies, which directly affects the operational and service effectiveness of the entire system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, reveals that the disparity between the level of material support and service provision, social and legal protection of personnel, and the increase in crime, coupled with a significant increase in the workload on employees due to the emergence of internal conflicts, has led to a substantial erosion of the core professional staff, a decline in the prestige of the service, and consequently, the departure of many qualified personnel from the field between 2014 and 2016 [2].

During the period since our country gained independence, the internal affairs system has carried out enormous tasks to preserve the country's independence, ensure the peace and security of our people, as well as during the dangerous periods when socio-political changes occurred. At the same time, based on the demands of the era, a number of reforms have been implemented in the internal affairs system over the past years regarding work with personnel, particularly in providing the system with qualified staff. However, when deeply analyzing the activities of the internal affairs bodies' system in working with personnel over the past quarter century, shortcomings in the selection and placement of personnel, formation of a personnel reserve, as well as organizing the service of internal affairs officers became clearly noticeable, and the personnel issue was elevated to the level of state policy.

In particular, in paragraph 1 of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2017, No. PP-3413 "On Measures for the Fundamental Improvement of the Procedure for Working with Personnel of Internal Affairs Bodies and the Organization of their Service"[3]: "The activities of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of personnel selection and placement, formation of their reserve, as well as the organization of service by employees of internal affairs bodies shall be recognized as unsatisfactory" - this statement is a clear confirmation of our opinion.

In today's rapidly changing era, ensuring the peace and tranquility of our people, combating crime and offenses, maintaining public order and security, and protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens are becoming increasingly important. The changes taking place in society necessitate fundamental reforms, including a reassessment of the activities of internal affairs bodies. Undoubtedly, one of the main directions of fundamental reform in the system of internal affairs bodies is the training, retraining, and professional development of internal affairs officers, as well as ensuring the organization of a continuous educational and career process.

Therefore, today comprehensive reforms are being implemented to improve the system of internal affairs bodies.

It should be noted that President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's visit to the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs on June 29, 2017, was not only a historic event but also instilled a sense of responsibility and enthusiasm for the work he had initiated in training personnel, working with them, and elevating personnel training to a qualitatively new level. During the visit, projects to be implemented in five priority areas for the development of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in 2017-2021 were reviewed. These include forming the teaching staff, consistently organizing the educational process, targeted training of candidates, assessing the qualifications of employees and the activities of sectoral services, establishing a fund for new innovative support, and strengthening its material and technical base.

Кадрлар сиёсатининг асосий вазифаси – кадрлар таркибини шакллантириш ва уларни ривожлантиришдир.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196 "On measures to raise the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of ensuring public safety and combating crime to a qualitatively new level."

In his holiday greetings to employees and veterans of the field on the occasion of the 30th anniversary of the establishment of internal affairs bodies and the celebration of October 25 - the Day of Internal Affairs Employees, our esteemed President also specifically addressed the direction of personnel training in internal affairs bodies. In particular, he emphasized that "a completely new system of specialist training has been established, and systematic measures are being taken to **ensure the promotion of employees based on their qualifications**, as well as to enhance the professional capacity of leaders. A modern two-tier higher education system, including bachelor's and master's degrees, has been introduced at the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, along with new educational mechanisms to ensure the integration of theory and practice in the educational process"[4].

Appendix 1 of this decree approved the "Roadmap" for further improvement of the internal affairs bodies system. The Roadmap consists of 4 general sections, with the 2nd section titled "Spiritual and educational work, **continuous training of personnel**, implementation of an effective mechanism for retraining and professional development."

Clause 11 of Section 2 stipulates the implementation of a qualitatively new system for training intellectual and professional personnel for internal affairs bodies and their career advancement. As a new system, we can particularly note the introduction of a continuous education-career system from September 1, 2021, which includes an educational process integrally linked with the rules of service.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed **Resolution No. PP-5076** dated April 15, 2021 "On Measures for Implementing a Qualitatively New System of Training Professional Personnel for Internal Affairs Bodies." According to this resolution, **a continuous education-career process system** will be introduced into the procedure for service in internal affairs bodies from September 1, 2021, which provides for the following:

mandatory study in the Academy's Master's program in the specialties "Organizational and Tactical Management" and "Organizational and Strategic Management" for appointment to the relevant leadership positions in internal affairs bodies;

the necessity for employees to undergo retraining and advanced training courses as one of the main requirements for assigning special ranks to employees and appointing rank-and-file and sergeant staff to officer positions.

In order to ensure the practical implementation of the above-mentioned Decrees and Resolutions, the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued **Order No. 310** on August 27, 2021, approving the "**Regulations on the Procedure for Organizing Training, Retraining and Advanced Training of Personnel in Internal Affairs Bodies Based on the System of Continuous Educational and Career Process.**"

Chapter 8 of these Regulations is titled "**Training of Management Personnel.**" According to it:

Training of managerial personnel for internal affairs bodies is organized through the master's program of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in the following areas:

Second-level "Organizational and Tactical Management";

First-level "Organizational and Strategic Management."

Today, due to the increasing state standards and requirements for the professional training of internal affairs personnel, the introduction of the "**Educational and Career Principle**"[5] has led to a notable improvement in the literacy of internal affairs officers who work among the public. The presence of specialists with deep professional and legal knowledge in the internal affairs bodies increases public confidence in the activities of these officers who serve as their protectors.

In order to protect the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, ensure the rule of law, and effectively fulfill their assigned tasks, the continuous improvement of qualifications and professional skills of internal affairs officers is an essential condition for personnel training based on the system of continuous educational and career processes.

The system of continuous education and career development for personnel consists of:

initial professional training;

specialized professional training;

retraining;

advanced training;

higher education;

training of managerial personnel;

postgraduate education;

service, combat, physical, and spiritual-educational training.

Each of these stages in the system of continuous education and career development has its own significance based on the specific requirements.

The system of continuous education and career development is organized and monitored. Planning and organization of training, retraining, and advanced training of personnel in internal affairs bodies are carried out using the capabilities of a unified database - the electronic platform "E-o'quv-kaguyega."

The database of the electronic platform "E-o'quv-kaguyega" encompasses the Department of Spiritual and Educational Work and Personnel Support of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Department for Organization of Educational Process, educational institutions, and personnel departments of internal affairs bodies by integrating them into a single electronic system.

The necessary information for the continuous education and career development process is securely stored in the database of the "E-o'quv-kaguyega" electronic platform, protected by hardware and software, and an "electronic portfolio" is created for each employee.

An employee's "electronic portfolio" is maintained throughout their entire career in the internal affairs bodies and serves to ensure:

Systematic and timely organization of employee retraining and professional development;

Monitoring the professional activities of employees from their date of appointment;

Individualizing the educational process for employees based on digital technologies, increasing their level of proficiency in using information technology capabilities;

Further improving distance learning for employees and creating favorable conditions for their independent learning;

Designated individuals appointed by the heads of structural and territorial divisions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and educational institutions are responsible for the accuracy, completeness, timely entry, and non-disclosure of all information entered into the database of the "E-learning-kaguyega" electronic platform.

Establishing stability, peace, and tranquility in society, maintaining public order, ensuring the security of individuals, society, and the state, and effectively organizing crime prevention are among the highest priorities of state policy. This involves developing initial professional knowledge, high patriotism, and moral qualities in law enforcement officers, enhancing their spiritual, educational, and legal knowledge, and creating an atmosphere of efficiency and positive relationships within teams to carry out activities as prescribed by relevant regulatory and departmental documents. The issues of building a legal democratic state, further socio-economic development of the country, improving the well-being of the population, and reliably protecting the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens are closely linked to the activities of highly qualified specialists in state bodies.

Reforms in the field of education within internal affairs bodies are currently no less relevant and practically significant than reforms in other areas. Continuing these reforms on a larger scale remains a requirement of our times.

Certainly, the successful fulfillment of tasks assigned to internal affairs bodies requires raising the level of professional knowledge of all personnel serving in the system. Indeed, only an employee who has truly embraced the noble idea that **"Serving the Motherland and the people with loyalty is our highest duty!"** [6] will perform their responsibilities wholeheartedly. To achieve this, we must implement educational work in an entirely new format and introduce new scientifically-based measures for training highly qualified personnel for the field.

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